
IMPACT OF ORGANISATIONAL JUSTICE ON EMPLOYEES' BURNOUT AND WORKPLACE CYNICISM IN DHL INTERNATIONAL LTD IN SOUTH-WEST, NIGERIA

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Article ID: GPH-IJBM-2026-2229

Abstract

The current research determined the pattern(s) of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) being practiced in DHL International LTD in South-West, Nigeria. This study determined the combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment); and ascertained the relative contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural); This study also examined the relationship between organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) and employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment); and determined the gender differences in the perception of employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment) based on organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional).

The study relied on primary data gathered using standard questionnaire that were self-administered to 212; The stratified sampling method was used to select respondents to reflect the strata of DHL Office in different states namely Lagos, Ekiti, Ogun, Ondo, Osun and Oyo and gender (male and female). Both primary and secondary methods of data collection were used to gather information on the research; Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data gathered in the study. The demographic information of the respondents was analyzed using descriptive statistics. While the hypothesis were tested using inferential statistics such as regression analysis, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, T-Test, and Chi-Square Analysis at the 0.05 level of significance.

The results revealed that there was a significant combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment) at (R) value of .895; this indicates strong positive interaction; Furthermore, it also concluded that, there is significant combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural) at (R) value of .635; The study summarizes that organizational justice negatively impact organizational cynicism, where organizational cynicism may reduce if organizational justice is high. The research therefore confirms that organizational justice is one of the most important factors that may overcome organizational cynicism. The empirical results indicated that employees perceive procedural-interactional justice as good practice and is more effective when all their concerns are heard before final decisions are made and employees are allowed to challenge or appeal job decisions made by their supervisors. The study provided useful and practical guidelines to organisations as to ensure effective strategising and management of organisational justice that could enhance their local and global competitiveness and long-term survival.

The study recommends that, Organisational justice should be carefully enshrined in various organizations. When carefully enshrined, it will reduce employees' burnout as well as the organizational cynicism. The findings of the study have contributed to the body of knowledge by developing a theoretical model of organisational justice in the private industry. The results of the study could also be replicated by other industries as to ensure successful implementation of fairness and organisational justice practices.

Keywords:

Organisational Justice, Employees' Burnout, Workplace Cynicism, Emotional Exhaustion, DHL International Ltd.

INTRODUCTION

Organisational justice, first articulated by Greenberg (1987), refers to employees' perceptions of fairness in organisational decisions, procedures and interpersonal treatment. These perceptions shape how employees evaluate their organisation's behaviour and the extent to which they feel valued or treated equitably. Organisational justice is commonly explained through three dimensions: distributive justice, which concerns fairness in outcomes such as rewards and resource allocation; procedural justice, which focuses on the consistency, transparency and impartiality of decision-making processes; and interactional justice, which reflects the degree of respect, dignity and quality of communication employees receive from supervisors.

Researchers have established that employees respond strongly to perceived fairness or unfairness. When justice is upheld, employees exhibit trust, satisfaction and stronger organisational citizenship behaviour (Coetzee, 2005; Rego & Chuna, 2006). However, when workers perceive injustice, the consequences are often negative, including emotional strain, anger, withdrawal and reduced commitment (Al-Shaalan, 2016; Al-Shakurji, 2008). The importance of justice becomes even more evident when considering how injustice contributes to burnout and workplace cynicism.

Burnout has gained significant attention in organisational research due to its profound psychological and behavioural impact. Defined as a state of emotional, physical and mental exhaustion, burnout develops when employees face prolonged stress and overwhelming job demands (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation and a reduced sense of personal accomplishment are the key components of burnout (de França et al., 2012). Several scholars have shown that burnout undermines job satisfaction, well-being and performance, while increasing absenteeism, turnover intention and interpersonal conflicts (Lambert et al., 2012; Wang, 2020).

Akintayo's contributions in this field are particularly notable. Akintayo (2010, 2012, 2022) consistently emphasises that employees' burnout is closely linked to organisational experiences and stressors encountered at work. He argues that burnout negatively affects employees' psychological, physical, social and intellectual well-being, making it a critical organisational challenge. His findings demonstrate that stress arising from role ambiguity, workload and organisational injustice significantly influences employees' attitude to work, job satisfaction and workplace behaviour.

Workplace cynicism, another central concept in this study, has also become a major concern in organisational behaviour. Cynicism involves negative beliefs, emotions and behaviours directed at the organisation, often emerging when employees perceive a mismatch between organisational values and managerial actions (Ince & Turan, 2011). Scholars such as Devi and Pojitha (2012) note that cynicism frequently arises when employees observe hypocrisy, unfair treatment or moral violations in organisational practices. Cynical employees tend to believe that leaders act in self-interest, disregard fairness and exploit workers, which increases distrust and reduces motivation.

The logistics environment, particularly within multinational organisations such as DHL International Ltd in South-West Nigeria, presents conditions in which justice perceptions can significantly influence employee outcomes. Operational pressure, tight delivery schedules, supervisory control and customer-focused demands create environments where fairness in workload distribution, communication and decision-making becomes essential. As Banks and Lomeli (2013) argue, organisational cynicism is associated with reduced commitment, low performance and higher turnover intentions – outcomes that can severely affect service-driven industries like logistics.

Despite extensive literature on organisational justice, burnout and cynicism, gaps remain regarding how these variables interact in private-sector logistics firms within the Nigerian context. While many studies have examined health care, education and public institutions, fewer have explored how different types of justice jointly or uniquely predict burnout and cynicism among logistics employees. Additionally, inconsistencies appear in existing findings, particularly regarding the role of distributive justice in predicting cynicism (Frenkel et al., 2012; Tayfur et al., 2013).

This study therefore investigates the patterns of organisational justice practised in DHL International Ltd and examines how fairness perceptions influence burnout and workplace cynicism. With evidence from Akintayo and other scholars showing that injustice intensifies stress and negative attitudes, this research seeks to provide empirical insight to strengthen fairness-based management practices within the logistics industry.

Statement of the Problem

Employees at DHL International Ltd in South-West Nigeria have increasingly perceived unfairness in salary distribution, bonuses, decision-making processes and interpersonal treatment from supervisors. Many feel excluded from important decisions and believe managers act with bias or lack respect. These perceptions have fuelled distrust, negative emotions, and declining confidence in organisational leadership.

Such injustice triggers burnout symptoms including emotional exhaustion, depersonalisation, and reduced personal accomplishment. It also enhances workplace cynicism, where employees doubt organisational sincerity and lose faith in leadership intentions. Despite these concerns, there is limited empirical evidence on how distributive, procedural, and interactional justice collectively shape burnout and cynicism within the logistics sector.

This study fills the gap by providing empirical insight into justice practices and their consequences for employee wellbeing and organisational effectiveness.

Research Questions

The following research questions were generated for the study:

- i. What is the combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment)?
- ii. What is the relative contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural)?
- iii. What is the relationship between employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment) and workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural)?

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to examine the impact of organizational justice on employees' burnout and workplace cynicism in DHL International Ltd in South-West, Nigeria. The following specific objectives were set to:

- i. determine the combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment);
- ii. ascertain the relative contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural);
- iii. investigate the relationship between employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment) and workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review examined existing concepts, theories and empirical findings related to organizational justice, employees' burnout and workplace cynicism, especially within organizational settings similar to DHL International Ltd in Southwest Nigeria. The review began with conceptual clarifications. Justice was described as a broad and evolving idea linked to fairness, equality and moral righteousness, while injustice was framed as unfairness or undeserved outcomes resulting from human misuse or neglect. The review further outlined the main causes of injustice, including economic inequality, racism and discrimination, and highlighted how employees typically respond to perceived injustice through emotional or irrational reactions when no effective redress exists.

Organizational justice was presented as employees' perception of fair treatment across distributive, procedural and interactional dimensions. Distributive justice concerns the fairness of resource allocation, procedural justice addresses the fairness of decision-making processes, and interactional justice relates to the quality of interpersonal treatment and information sharing. The literature identifies organizational justice as critical because it promotes trust, improves employee performance, supports citizenship behavior and strengthens social, economic and ethical relationships in the workplace. It also reduces negative outcomes such as low commitment, burnout, turnover intention, and counterproductive work behaviors.

Further, the review emphasized that organizational justice yields benefits such as trust enhancement, improved employee performance, and stronger cooperative behavior. Determinants of organizational justice were outlined, including equitable compensation, fair employee selection, justified promotion and impersonal but professional relations. The consequences of justice were situated in improved job satisfaction, organizational citizenship behavior and organizational commitment.

Burnout was explained as a psychological syndrome involving emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and reduced personal accomplishment. Classic work by Maslach and colleagues demonstrated that burnout emerges from chronic exposure to stressful work

environments, not only in human-service professions but across modern occupations. The causes of burnout were grouped into mismatches in workload, control, reward, community, fairness, and personal values. Signs of burnout include emotional, physical, social, and work-related symptoms. The review presented burnout as a major barrier to effective job performance and overall employee wellbeing.

The review also addressed workplace cynicism as a negative attitude toward the organization characterized by distrust, anger, frustration, and pessimism. Cynicism was shown to be closely tied to burnout, perceptions of injustice, unmet expectations, and failed organizational change efforts. Its three dimensions cognitive, affective, and behavioural were described as involving beliefs that the organization lacks integrity, emotional reactions such as shame or anger, and visible behaviours such as criticism, complaints and withdrawal. The literature noted that workplace cynicism is associated with reduced organizational commitment, performance, satisfaction and citizenship behaviour and increased turnover intentions.

Finally, the theoretical foundations of the study were reviewed. Equity Theory emphasized fairness in input-output relationships and predicted that perceived inequity creates psychological tension that motivates employees to seek balance. Justice Judgment Theory proposed that fairness arises from adherence to distributive and procedural rules. Psychological theories of justice focused on self-interest and relational models, arguing that fairness promotes identity, belonging and cooperation. Integrative theories such as fairness heuristic theory, uncertainty management theory and fairness theory explained why justice perceptions guide behaviour. Reactive and proactive content theories contrasted how individuals respond to unfair treatment versus how they participate in forming fair structures.

Overall, the literature consistently indicated that organizational justice is central to shaping employee attitudes and behaviours while burnout and workplace cynicism represent major negative outcomes of injustice, work pressure, and organizational inefficiencies.

Empirical Review on Organizational Justice

Empirical studies consistently reveal that organizational justice has significant and positive effects on key employee and organizational outcomes. Ajala (2019) found strong relationships among the three dimensions of organizational justice and job satisfaction, and concluded that the level of job satisfaction is a direct response to the perceived existence of organizational justice at the workplace. Similarly, Ogwuche, Musa and Nyam (2018) showed that perceived organizational justice significantly and positively influence job performance and that perceived organizational justice and organizational climate significantly and jointly influence job performance.

Studies by Evawere, Eketu and Needorn (2018), Faruk and Yil (2016), Karanja (2016), and John Omogeafe Ohioyenya and Evans Osaruwmen Eguavoen (2019) further revealed that strong correlations exist between dimensions of organizational justice and workers' citizenship behaviour, task performance, organizational commitment and employee engagement. Several other investigations (for example, Gofi et al., 2020; Aeknarajindawat and Jernsittiparset, 2020;

Rahman et al., 2015; Ali, 2016; Percunda et al., 2020; Sembiring et al., 2020; Akram et al., 2020; Fiaz et al., 2020; Hoa et al., 2020; Pimentel et al., 2020; Jameel et al., 2020; Suifan et al., 2017; Swalh et al., 2017; Ponnu and Chuah, 2010; Kalay, 2016; Wang et al., 2010; Arab and Atan, 2018; Imamoglu et al., 2019; Novitasari et al., 2020) also reported that distributive, procedural, interactional, interpersonal and informational justice significantly influence job satisfaction, organizational commitment, performance, turnover intention, organizational citizenship behaviour, perceived organizational support, knowledge sharing, firm performance and organizational outcomes.

Overall, the empirical findings indicate that organizational justice significantly and positively impacts employees' attitudes and behaviours and that fairness in procedures, distribution of outcomes and interpersonal treatment is critical for improving performance, satisfaction, commitment and other desirable organizational outcomes.

Empirical Review for Employees' Burnout

Empirical evidence shows that employees' burnout has adverse effects on job satisfaction and performance. Kehinde Agboola (2020) found that major causes of burnout include emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, while personal achievement increases employee job satisfaction; insufficient motivation, low organisational support and high job demand could lead to employees' burnout, and there is an inverse relationship between job burnout and employee satisfaction which makes them perform below expectations.

Warraich et al. (2014) revealed that workload, role conflict, and inadequate monetary reward are the prime reasons of causing stress in employees, and this stress reduces their efficiency, implying a negative relationship between employees' burnout and performance. Tahir (2011) showed that intrinsic and extrinsic variables have positive effect on academic performance of college teachers and found significant differences between academic performance of teachers of public and private colleges. Cross Ogohi Daniel (2019) also concluded that employees' burnout can affect employee performance when stress is not handled well, as absenteeism, turnover and medical compensation increase and productivity decreases, and that huge dissatisfaction lowers performance.

Empirical Review for Workplace Cynicism

The empirical review on workplace cynicism emphasizes a close relationship between organizational cynicism and burnout. Cynic personnel experience apathy, alienation, despair, disappointment and a higher level of emotional exhaustion, and burnout is described as a psychological syndrome including emotional exhaustion, cynicism (or depersonalization) and inefficacy or lack of personal accomplishment. Cynicism is described as a defensive reaction of coping burnout, and emotional exhaustion is significantly associated with organizational cynicism, boosting negative expressions towards work in the organization.

Studies report that employees who are emotionally consumed experience emotional fatigue, decreased efficacy and productivity, and various negative outcomes such as being late to work,

absenteeism and job leaving. One study shows that there is a strong relationship between burnout and organizational cynicism, and that cynicism mostly affects staff in a negative way, especially emerging as emotional exhaustion and burnout. It is further noted that both the violation of psychological agreement and organizational cynicism contain unfulfilled expectations; the violation of psychological agreement causes cynicism and cynicism leads to emotional exhaustion.

In many studies, the depersonalization dimension of burnout is used as the synonym of cynicism, including negative, senseless and excessively distant reactions to various parts of the job. Empirical findings in Nigerian banks also reveal a significant relationship between job burnout and organizational cynicism, and recommend that employees should be given breaks and time off to guard against emotional exhaustion since it has a significant relationship with organizational cynicism.

Research Hypotheses

In line with the stated objectives above, the following hypotheses were formulated:

H₀₁: There is no significant combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment).

H₀₂: There is no significant combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural).

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment) and workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioral).

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which was considered appropriate because no variables were manipulated and data were collected from a sample to describe the characteristics of the population. The design enabled an accurate and systematic examination of the impact of organizational justice on employees' burnout and workplace cynicism in DHL International Ltd, South West Nigeria.

The study was conducted across the six states in South West Nigeria: Ekiti, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo, Osun and Oyo. DHL International Ltd is widely recognized for excellence in international shipping and courier services, with extensive logistics operations that demand high employee involvement. The zone is predominantly occupied by Yoruba people and DHL International Ltd was noted as the World's Best Workplace in 2022.

The study population consisted of all employees of DHL International Ltd across the six states. Table 3.1 shows the distribution of the 468 core staff who constituted the population.

TABLE 1: STRATIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BY STATES

<i>LOGISTICS INDUSTRY</i>	<i>STATES</i>	<i>POPULATION</i>
DHL Int'l Ltd, South-West, Nigeria	Lagos	296
DHL Int'l Ltd, South- West, Nigeria	Ogun	29
DHL Int'l Ltd, South- West, Nigeria	Oyo	70
DHL Int'l Ltd, South- West, Nigeria	Osun	21
DHL Int'l Ltd, South- West, Nigeria	Akure	37
DHL Int'l Ltd, South- West, Nigeria	Ekiti	15
TOTAL		468

Source: Human Resource Unit, Head Quarters, DHL International Ltd, Lagos, 2023

The sample size was determined using Yamane's (1967) formula:

$$n = N / (1 + N(e^2)) \quad (1)$$

$$n = 468 / (1 + 468(0.05^2)) \quad (2)$$

$$n = 468 / 2.17 \quad (3)$$

$$n = \mathbf{215} \quad (4)$$

This represented 46 percent of the population. Proportionate and simple random sampling techniques were used so every element had an equal chance of selection. Table 2 presents the distribution of the sample.

TABLE 2: SAMPLE DISTRIBUTION BY STATE

<i>NAME OF ORGANISATION</i>	<i>STATES</i>	<i>NO OF EMPLOYEES</i>	<i>NO OF RESPONDENT 46%</i>
DHL Int'l Ltd, South-West, Nigeria	Lagos	296	137
DHL Int'l Ltd, South-West, Nigeria	Ogun	29	14
DHL Int'l Ltd, South-West, Nigeria	Oyo	70	33
DHL Int'l Ltd, South-West, Nigeria	Osun	21	10

DHL Int'l Ltd, South-West, Nigeria	Akure	37	18
DHL Int'l Ltd, South-West, Nigeria	Ekiti	15	7
TOTAL	----	468	219

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2023

Both primary and secondary data were used. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to managerial and non-managerial staff to assess organizational justice, employees' burnout, and workplace cynicism. Secondary data were sourced from textbooks, journals, reports, and other published materials.

The research instrument consisted of four sections (A–D). Section A collected demographic information. Section B measured organizational justice using three subscales: Distributive Justice Scale (10 items; reliability 0.79), Procedural Justice Scale (10 items; reliability 0.90), and Interactional Justice Scale (10 items; reliability 0.86). All items were measured on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

Section C assessed employees' burnout using the Maslach Burnout Inventory with three subscales: Emotional Exhaustion Scale (reliability 0.75), Depersonalization Scale (reliability 0.71), and Personal Accomplishment Scale (reliability 0.87). Items were rated on the same 4-point Likert scale.

Section D assessed workplace cynicism through three subscales: Cognitive Scale (reliability 0.77), Affective Scale (reliability 0.82), and Behavioural Scale (reliability 0.75), also measured on a 4-point Likert scale.

Content validity was strengthened through expert judgment. The supervisor and relevant specialists reviewed and approved the instrument. A cover letter assured respondents of confidentiality and voluntary participation.

Instrument reliability was confirmed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to test model significance at a 95 percent confidence level and a 0.05 level of significance. Adjusted R-square was used to determine variations in the dependent variables.

Administration of the questionnaires followed official approval through a letter of introduction from the Department of Human Resource Development. Research assistants in each state supported distribution and retrieval. Respondents were assured of anonymity, and data collection took approximately four weeks due to work schedules across locations.

The completed questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, means, standard deviations and distribution tables. Inferential statistics, specifically

linear regression analysis, were used to test the study's hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis One: There is no significant combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment).

TABLE 3: A SUMMARY OF THE REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AND EMPLOYEES' BURNOUT.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.895 ^a	.801	.799	2.14239
<i>*p<0.05 a. Predictors: (Constant), Interactional, Distributive, Procedural</i>				

Table 3 shows the model summary of the regression analysis of interaction between combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) and employees' burnout with (R) value of .895. This indicates strong positive interaction between the organizational justice variables and employees' burnout. At a 5% level of significance, the size of the interaction is likewise statistically significant. Organizational justice account for roughly 80 percent of employees' burnout among the DHL staff in South-West, Nigeria, according to the R Square value of 0.801. Other variables that are not contained within this model but represented under the stochastic error term account for the remaining 19.9% of the variability.

TABLE 4: REGRESSION ANALYSIS SHOWING SIGNIFICANCE OF PREDICTORS ON EMPLOYEES' BURNOUT

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3854.298	3	1284.766	279.916	.000 ^b
	Residual	954.683	208	4.590		
	Total	4808.981	211			
<i>a. Dependent Variable: Employees' Burnout Variables</i>						
<i>b. Predictors: (Constant), Interactional, Distributive, Procedural</i>						

Table 4 shows that organizational justice variables (distributive, procedural and interactional) significantly predicted the level of employees' burnout. $F(3, 211) = 279.916, p < 0.05$. F – statistical indicates that the overall regression model is highly statistically significant in terms of its goodness of fit since the value of $F_{tab} > F_{cal}$. Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected. The study concludes that there is positive significant of combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment) in DHL International Ltd in South West, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural).

TABLE 5: A SUMMARY OF THE REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AND WORKPLACE CYNICISM.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.635 ^a	.404	.395	2.98037
<i>*p<0.05 a. Predictors: (Constant), Interactional, Distributive, Procedural</i>				

Table 5 shows the model summary of the regression analysis of interaction between combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) and workplace cynicism with (R) value of .635. This indicates positive interaction between the organizational justice variables and workplace cynicism. At a 5% level of significance, the size of the interaction is likewise statistically significant. Organizational justice account for roughly 40 percent of workplace cynicism among the DHL staff in South-West, Nigeria, according to the R² value of 0.404. Other variables that are not contained within this model but represented under the stochastic error term account for the remaining 59.6% of the variability.

TABLE 6: REGRESSION ANALYSIS SHOWING SIGNIFICANCE OF PREDICTORS ON WORKPLACE CYNICISM

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1250.867	3	416.956	46.941	.000b
	Residual	1847.586	208	8.883		
	Total	3098.453	211			
<i>a. Dependent Variable: Workplace Cynicism Variables</i>						
<i>b. Predictors: (Constant), Interactional, Distributive, Procedural</i>						

Table 6 shows that organizational justice variables (distributive, procedural and interactional) significantly predicted the level of workplace cynicism variables. $F(3, 211) = 46.941, p < 0.05$ – statistical indicates that the overall regression model is highly statistically significant in terms of its goodness of fit since the value of $F_{tab} > F_{cal}$. Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected. The study concludes that there is significant combined contribution of organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) to workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural) in DHL industry in South West Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment) and workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioral)

		Workplace Cynicism	Employees Burnout
Workplace Cynicism	Pearson Correlation	1	.565**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
Employees Burnout	Pearson Correlation	.565**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As shown in Table 7, workplace cynicism variables show significant positive relationship with employees' burnout variables. Employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment) has the correlation value of $r = 0.57$ with workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioral). The variables were statistically significant at 99% confident limit and sig 0.000. Thus, there is significant correlation between employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment) and workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioral), about 56.5%. This means that there is positive correlation between employees' burnout and workplace cynicism. Null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the study concludes that there is significant relationship positive correlation between employee's burnout and workplace cynicism in DHL International Ltd, in South-West, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

This section explained the findings of the results under each hypothesis tested under the study. However, the study on the impact of organizational justice on employees' burnout and workplace cynicism in DHL International Ltd, in South-West, Nigeria and its findings are discussed below:

It was indicated that strong positive interaction exists between organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) and employees' burnout. The study findings are in line with the conclusion of Liljegren, and Ekberg, (2009), who reported that global justice construct showed better goodness-of-fit indices than the threefold justice construct but a differentiated organizational justice concept could give valuable information about health related risk factors: if they are structural (distributive justice), procedural (procedural justice) or inter-personal (interactional justice).

The second hypothesis tested on the significant combined contribution of organizational justice to workplace cynicism and findings are discussed below:

The organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) show significant contribution with workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural). This corroborates with Kwantes, and Bond (2019), found that the social cynicism is related to employees' organizational cynicism when conceptualized as a cognition, but not when conceptualized as an

affect or a behaviour in part-time employees. Also, organizational justice and autonomy as moderators of the relationship between social has significant effects on the organizational cynicism. Also, Shaharruddin, Ahmad, and Musa, (2016), found that procedural justice was found to be the strongest organizational justice dimension that significantly influencing organizational cynicism level. Likewise, Erdogdu, (2018) reported that the higher the perception of organizational justice behaviors, the less the organizational cynicism. Moreover, there was a positive significant correlation between organizational silence and organizational cynicism.

The third hypothesis tested on the relationship between employees' burnout and workplace cynicism and findings are discussed below:

Workplace cynicism show significant positive relationship with employees' burnout. This is in line with empirical studies like, Butt, and Yazdani, (2021), reported that workplace incivility has significant and positive association with counterproductive work behavior. While, emotional exhaustion and cynicism partially mediate positive association between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behavior. Moreover, psychological capital in interaction with workplace incivility has significant moderating impact and weakens the positive association between workplace incivility and counterproductive work behavior.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study examined the impact of organizational justice on employees' burnout and workplace cynicism in DHL International Ltd in South-West Nigeria. The findings revealed that organizational justice has a significant impact on both employees' burnout and workplace cynicism.

Conclusion

The study set out to examine how organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) relates to and contributes to employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment) and workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural). It also focused on the relationships among organizational justice, workplace cynicism and employees' burnout.

The results showed strong and significant positive relationships between the dimensions of organizational justice and workplace cynicism. As revealed in Table 4.7, distributive justice correlated with workplace cynicism at $r = 0.549$, procedural justice at $r = 0.627$ and interactional justice at $r = 0.534$, all statistically significant at the 1% level. This implies that there is a strong significant positive correlation between organizational justice variables (Distributive = 54.9%, Procedural = 62.7%, Interactional = 53.4%) and workplace cynicism. The null hypothesis was rejected, and the study concludes that there is a significant relationship between organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) and workplace cynicism (cognitive, affective and behavioural) in DHL International Ltd in South-West Nigeria.

The research further summarizes that organizational justice negatively impacts organizational cynicism in the sense that organizational cynicism may reduce when organizational justice is

high. The study therefore confirms that organizational justice is one of the most important factors that may overcome organizational cynicism.

In addition, organizational justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) recorded a much higher mean score than employees' burnout (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment), and the difference was large enough to be statistically significant. The mean score for employees' burnout ($M = 12.4$) was significantly lower than the mean score for organizational justice ($M = 34.4$). Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a significant difference in the perception of employees' burnout based on organizational justice among staff of DHL in South-West Nigeria.

The study also highlighted factors that contribute to burnout, including work overload (quantitative and qualitative), role conflict, role ambiguity, lack of autonomy, interpersonal conflict, organizational politics, job insecurity, lack of social support, lack of support from supervisors and organizational trust. Burnout is further affected by personality and demographic factors such as internal and external locus of control, skill level, coordination expertise, age and job tenure.

The empirical results indicated that employees perceive procedural–interactional justice as good practice and more effective when their concerns are heard before final decisions are made and when they are allowed to challenge or appeal job decisions made by their supervisors. Employees also believe that everyone should be treated with kindness and consideration and that management should be sensitive to their personal needs.

The findings further revealed that employees perceive distributive justice as effective when their work schedule is fair in accordance with their job description, when they are compensated according to the skills required for their jobs and when recognition is based on the merit of each employee's performance and criteria are consistently applied equally to all employees.

Overall, the study concludes that organizational justice is a critical factor in reducing workplace cynicism and managing employees' burnout in DHL International Ltd in South-West Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. **Institutionalize organizational justice**
Organizational justice should be carefully enshrined in organizational policies and practices. When properly embedded, it will boost employees' performance as well as organizational performance. This can be achieved by adopting equitable compensation and incentives, ensuring proper placement of employees, establishing positive employer–employee relations and promoting corporate social responsibility.
- ii. **Monitoring and assessment of justice practices**
Organizations should monitor and assess whether they have failed in exhibiting organizational justice to their employees. Government should establish bodies to checkmate organizational justice in various organizations. This will enhance organizational performance and have a positive impact on the national economy.
- iii. **Strengthen corporate social responsibility and staff bonding**
There should be corporate social responsibility initiatives and internal programmes or extra-curricular activities that strengthen relationships among personnel. Such activities can help build trust, reduce cynicism and foster a more cohesive workforce.
- iv. **Expand future research samples**
Future studies should use larger sample sizes to test similar hypotheses in order to uncover more revelations and deepen understanding of the relationships among organizational justice, burnout and workplace cynicism in other contexts and industries.
- v. **Enhance procedural–interactional justice in private industry**
Private organizations that apply procedural–interactional justice should make decisions in an unbiased manner, treat employees with dignity and respect, be sensitive to employees' personal needs and provide complete information when requested. This will reinforce perceptions of fairness and reduce cynicism.
- vi. **Strengthen distributive justice practices**
For distributive justice to be effective in private industry, organizations should ensure that work schedules are fair and consistent with job descriptions, compensate employees according to their acquired skills, base recognition on the merit of each employee's performance and apply promotion criteria consistently and equally to all employees.

Implementing these recommendations will help organizations, particularly logistics companies like DHL International Ltd, to reduce burnout and workplace cynicism, improve employee wellbeing and strengthen overall organizational effectiveness.

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